

EDGE IMPACT DAMAGE SCENARIO ON STIFFENED COMPOSITE STRUCTURE

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Abstract

Low velocity / low energy edge impact and almost-static experiments have been carried out on carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) structures. A drop-weight testing machine was used to impact four different UD laminates at 10, 20 and 35 J impact energies. In parallel, an almost-static study has been conducted in order to compare its results with the impact one. Compression after impact tests will supply the residual behavior. The results show that the static and dynamic behaviors are different. The fiber properties control the initial impact stiffness. In addition, regardless of the impact energy and stacking, a specific "crushing plateau" phenomenon appears. In the almost-static indentation case the properties of the matrix control the initial indentation stiffness. A simplified analytical impact model is provided trying to explain the difference between static and dynamic edge impact regardless the stacking or impact energy. It actually well represents the dynamic and static initial stiffness and the crushing plateau. The experimental results will be compared to a numerical model in order to simulate the impact and compression after impact damage.

1 Introduction

Composites are widely used in aeronautical engineering development. These structures are especially vulnerable to foreign object impacts during manufacturing operations or maintenance and in the same time significant damage can occur and yet be undetectable by visual inspection [1]. This can dramatically reduce their residual properties. To certify these structures in aeronautics, it is necessary to demonstrate their resistance to residual charges dependent to the impact damage detectability [8].

The current edge impact detectability threshold policy in aeronautics industry is based on dent depth and crack length (Fig.1).

Many studies have been carried out on composite skin impact issues and the damage mechanism is now fairly well controlled ([4] and [5]). However a lack of knowledge still exists on the edge impact

phenomena [7], a free edge stringer for example (Fig.2).

Today, solutions to protect structures submitted to edge impacts are heavy and must be improved. Therefore it is important to study more precisely this particular impact and to define the damage scenario in order to identify the parameters that affect the residual after impact strength. Then it will be possible to improve the stringer's impact damage tolerance.

The main goal of this research is to carry out impact and compression after impact experiments in order to establish the damage scenario. A vertical drop-weight testing device was used to perform the edge impacts on different stacking laminates. At the same time, an almost-static study has been conducted in order to compare its results with the impact ones. Microscope cross sections and X-rays analysis were then studied to visualize the damage scenario.

Then, compression after impact tests are also in progress to determine the residual strength after edge impact.

2 Material and methods

2.1 Specimen definition

First of all, a test specimen has been designed to perform preliminary understanding of the phenomenon. It is representative of the current needs identified above. T700/M21 Uni-directionnal (UD) carbon prepreg was selected. It is typically used by aircraft manufacturer. This material is well known [10] and its properties are given in Tab.1.

A carbon fabric woven / epoxy M21/46280 was also used and its properties are given in Tab.2. Four different stacking were defined:

Stacking 1 : [90, 45, 0₃, -45, 0₂, 45, 90, -45, 0]_s , 6 mm-thick for 24 plies.

Stacking 2 : [90₂, -45₂, 0₄, 45₂, 0₂]_s , 6 mm-thick for 24 plies.

Stacking 3 : [45₂, 0₂, -45₂, 0₄, 90₂]_s , 6 mm-thick for 24 plies.

Stacking 4 : [Fabric woven (0/90), -45₂, 0₄, 45₂, 0₂]_s, 5.6 mm-thick for 22 plies.

Thicknesses are consistent with the laboratory test facilities and are in agreement with the industrial ranges. These stacking are very oriented: 50 % plies at 0°, which matches well with industrial stacking in such stiffener issues. Stacking 1 is representative of an aeronautical industrial layup (symmetrical, well beaten, no delta at the interface greater than 45°, outside 90° plies to limit 0° plies damage in case of flank impact). Stacking 2 limits the interfaces number of different orientations plies, which will be of great interest in modeling, and will shorten the numerical model development. Case 3 follows the same philosophy and has better buckling resistance due to the outside 45° plies. Stacking 4 is equivalent with stacking 2 but it has a fabric woven instead of the two 90° outer plies. The initial goal was to contain the damage and this allows investigating the fabric woven residual strength influence.

Finally the specimen size is representative of a stringer structure: 150 mm long, 60 mm high with 30 mm free outside boundary conditions (Fig.3).

2.2 Impact Experiment

Impact experiment is designed to create representative damage of those actually produced on composite structures service life. Impact tests are performed at a low-speed thanks to a drop-weight falling down on the four defined stacking. No edge impact standard experiment still exists, that is why an original setup has been design.

All tests are performed with the same hemispherical 16 mm-diameter impactor, 2.368 kg-weight. The specimen is clamped in a specific designed edge impact tool (Fig. 3) and locked on half of its height. It will then remain 30 mm clearance subjected to impact. The objective is to avoid a costly stiffener manufacturing and at the same time to be representative of a real impact on a stiffener. In addition it still remains consistent for the damage study preventing the damage to propagate to the boundary conditions.

The edge impact tool is composed of a steel support and a shim (Fig.3) allowing the specimen to be locked under constant pressure. This assembly represents an housing connection (30 mm high of the specimen locked and 30 mm free under edge impact).

This impact device allows the drop of a specific impactor at a defined high, fixed to carriage guided by a rail. Given the specimen thickness, the drop tower average position does not exceed 1 mm. The specimen damage related acquisition parameters are initial speed and impact force.

Typically, because of the sensor position (between the mass and the impactor tip), the impact force (F) is not the measured load sensor one (F_{measured}) but should be modulated according to the following equation (1), where m_{impactor} is the impactor mass and m_{impactor_tip} is the impactor tip mass:

$$F_{real} = \frac{m_{impactor}}{m_{impactor} - m_{impactor_tip}} . F_{measured} \quad (1)$$

Impactor displacement is obtained with a double integration of the acceleration which is obtained thanks to the force [9]. The force-displacement graph gives a first clue of the specimen behavior during the impact experiment (Fig.4). Impact kinetic energy is represented by the area under upswing part of the force (A-B Fig.4) and the area under downswing part of the force (B-C Fig.4) represents the elastic released energy. Therefore, the difference between these two energies is the absorbed energy. Otherwise, it is represented by the area inside the force-displacement curve.

2.3 Indentation experiment

In parallel, an almost-static study has been conducted in order to compare its results with the impact ones and to emphasize the damage phenomenon. The major interest lies on the indenter displacement mastering. That allows to compare the almost static and dynamic experiments for the same impactor displacement. An electromechanical 100 kN INSTRON 4206 device is used to carry out experiments. The force is given by the device sensor. The indenter displacement is measured with an LVDT as close as possible to the impactor/indenter. The displacement speed equals 0.2 mm/min.

2.4 Controls

First of all, an ultrasonic check (C-SCAN) is carried out before impact to ensure that specimens are healthy.

After impact, specimens are analyzed thanks to three technologies (Fig.5). Indeed crack length can be measured on the top edge of the specimen (Fig.5.a) by visual inspection. Then an X-Rays (XR) is proceeded in order to reveal cracks and delaminated area (Fig.5.b). Finally the specimen is cut and microscope cross sections are performed (Fig.5.c). These cuts are completed with scanning electron microscopy (SEM) figures in order to visualize specific plies damage more precisely.

Cut sections have highlighted kink-bands [6], a local instability for fibers subjected to compression in fiber direction.

3 Results et discussion

3.1 Impact

Three energies of 10, 20 and 35 J are used to study the damage (Fig.6) for each stacking. The force-displacement curves give a lot of information. First of all, the force starts climbing sharply and a maximum force is reached. Since then it falls sharply but flattened off at a plateau of around 6250 N whatever the stacking and the impact energy (Fig.6 and Fig.7). The impactor displacement is finally inversed, the force suffers a drop and a permanent indentation remains.

To the author knowledge, no other work has determined edge impact degradation modes and their chronology. An impact damage scenario is proposed where a leading role is given to the wedge effect, the development of kink bands followed by the creation of a crushing phenomenon (Fig.7).

- From step 1 to step 2: the contact surface between the impactor tip and the specimen grows. At the beginning, kink bands appear in the plies parallel with the impact direction (Fig.8). The force starts climbing sharply and almost linearly until an impactor force corresponding to a crushing stress (cf **4.Analytical model**).

- From step 2 to step 3: the force falls sharply due to crushing and a wedge effect appears creating matrix shear cracks that propagate through neighboring plies of different orientations.

- From step 3 to step 4: the force reaches a plateau and interfaces delamination follows. The crushing continues. A swelling appears when the cracks reach outer plies (after about 0.5 mm impactor displacement). The remaining debris under the impactor help to push outer plies out of the side plane and the swelling increases delamination spread.

- From step 4 to step 5: the discharge begins. The impactor direction changes its direction and the stress drops gradually. Permanent indentation and out of plane swelling remain for a zero strength. An important damage remains inside the structure (Fig.9).

In general, edge impact causes all interfaces delamination. From a quantitative point of view, maximum crack length evolution (Fig.10), depth and surface delaminated depending on the impact energy can be represented. Rationally, higher is the impact energy, the larger the crack length is. In addition, the crack lengths are almost identical for different stacking. The residual dent being predominant in residual stress, it is also interesting to plot the delaminated area evolution versus this permanent dent. It represents a first approximation of the specimen damage according to the after impact permanent indentation (Fig. 11). Finally the damage aspect can be drawn for each stacking. These diagrams show the wedge effect, the matrix transverse shear and interfaces delamination (Fig.12).

3.2 Indentation

We clearly see that there is no Static / Dynamic equivalence when the impact force-displacement and indentation curves are superimposed (Fig.13) for each stacking. This is even more striking when studying an equivalent indentation displacement than during impact by X-Rays (Fig.14).

In addition, thanks to the impactor displacement mastering, experiments could be stopped and cut sections have been proceed. Kink bands propagation on the first almost-linear force climbing (Fig.15) were emphasized.

4 Analytical model

To deepen the non Static / Dynamic equivalence, differences in stiffness at the beginning of each test, static and dynamic, can be noted (Fig.13). Then a force "PATEAU" just after the stress peak can be identified on the impact graph. In this paper an analytical determination of these phenomena is proposed. The objective is to understand the damage phenomena.

Studying crushing researches [3], a similar force plateau following the stress peak appears in the crushing graphs. This force step represents a phenomenon similar to "plasticity" during crushing experiment. It is proportional to an average crushing stress value of -270 MPa, and this, whatever the relative plies orientation to the load. This value is very close to the allowable transverse direction

stress of T700/M21: $Y_c = -250$ MPa. Y_c becomes an equivalent average crushing stress σ_c Avg. The projected contact surface (impactor / specimen) was studied on microscopic binocular pictures. An average projected area of impact was measured $S_{pi} \approx 25$ mm² (Fig.16 and Fig.17). It is noted that in the case of a 35 J impact, the outer plies are severely damaged and a projected impact area determination does not really make sense because of the specimen damage.

This surface S_{pi} can be multiplied by the allowable stress through the transverse direction. The "**CRUSHING PLATEAU**" force of approximately 6250 N is obtained. This curve is superimposed on the impact tests curve for each stacking (Fig.8).

In addition, the initial stiffness of the impact test is higher than the static one. The compressive stress actually seen by each ply is supposed to be dependent on orientation and in proportion to the contact surface. For 0° plies the compressive stress is $Y_c = -250$ MPa, For 90° plies the compressive stress is $X_c = -1280$ MPa. For $\pm 45^\circ$ plies the choice was made to use the X_c and Y_c resulting components projected on the impact axis X_{45° according to the following equation (2) (Fig.18):

$$X_{45^\circ} = -\sqrt{X_c^2 + Y_c^2} \cdot \cos(\theta) = -1082 \text{ MPa} \quad (2)$$

Where θ is defined in Fig.18. For example, for a 0.3 mm impactor displacement in the stacking 2 specimen, the total contact area between the impactor and plies specimen is divided into: 70 % oriented at 0°, 27.5 % oriented at 45° and 2.5 % oriented at -45° (Fig.19). With this method, depending on the impactor penetration in the specimen, the values of the "**DYNAMIC STIFFNESS**" curve is calculated (Fig.13). It is superimposed on the impact test curve for each stacking. In addition, the maximum force is the intersection between the dynamic stiffness curve and an impactor displacement of 0.5 mm which corresponds to $S_{pi} \approx 25$ mm² (Fig.17) where the crushing appears. Knowing the impact energy, the force-displacement diagram curve during an edge impact can be modeled.

In the almost static indentation the following assumption is made: the material behaves directly in

crushing with a weaker stiffness than in impact. Then the stress is identical regardless of the plies orientation compared to the compression load. This stress is equal to Y_c . This stress Y_c is multiply by the projected theoretical surface of the impactor during the first moments of the indentation experiment. The values of the "**STATIC STIFFNESS**" curve are obtained (Fig.13) for each stacking.

5 Conclusion

Experimental edge impacts at 10, 20 and 35 J were performed on different stacking specimens. Then, almost-static tests were carried out in order to understand the phenomena and to compare the crushing behavior to the dynamic one. Regarding the damage scenario, studies lead to the following conclusions:

1. If fibers are oriented in the impact direction, then kink bands are created (dynamic and static).
2. For the dynamic impact. Whatever energy (10, 20 and 35 J) and for each stacking (1 to 4), the force-displacement curves have similar initial stiffness. This initial "DYNAMIC STIFFNESS" can be modeled multiplying the contact surface of each fiber orientation with the impactor by the fiber orientation compressive stress. So the fiber properties control the initial impact stiffness.
3. Similarly, regardless of the energy (10, 20 and 35 J) and stacking (1 to 4), a specific crushing plateau phenomenon appears. This "CRUSHING PLATEAU" can be modeled multiplying an average crushing stress of -250 Mpa by an average projected area of impact $S_{pi} \approx 25 \text{ mm}^2$.
4. The maximum force can be modeled as the intersection between the dynamic stiffness curve and an impactor displacement of 0.5 mm where the crushing appears.
5. Stacking has a small influence on the impact damage.

6. There is no equivalence between Static / Dynamic edge impact.
7. In the almost-static indentation case, the material behaves directly in crushing. This initial "STATIC STIFFNESS" can be modeled multiplying an average crushing stress of -250 Mpa by the projected theoretical surface of the impactor during the first moments of the indentation experiment. So the properties of the matrix control the initial indentation stiffness.

The results of experimental tests will be then compared with a numerical impact model that consists of interface elements to describe the matrix cracks and volume elements [2]. Finally, a numerical prediction of the residual strength after impact will reduce the masses to avoid expensive tests, and thus shorten the development time.

Fig. 1. Edge impact detection policy

Fig. 2. Edge impact principle

Fig. 3. Edge impact tool principle

Fig. 4. Impact force-displacement curve

Fig. 5. After impact controls

Fig. 6. Force-displacement curves of the stacking 4 impacted at 10, 20 and 35 J

Fig. 7. Comparison of the force-displacement curves for the four stacking (20 J impact)

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Fig. 8. Stacking 3 Kink bands (SEM cut section- 10 J impact)

Fig. 9. Stacking 3 XR damage (35 J impact)

Fig. 10. Maximum crack length versus impact energy

Fig. 11. Delaminated area versus permanent dent

Fig. 12. Damage aspect drawings for each stacking

Fig. 13. Stacking 3 indentation and impact experiment superposition

Fig. 14. Stacking 4 impact and indentation X-Rays (20 J equivalent)

Fig. 16. Stacking 3 projected area of impact measurement

Fig. 15. Stacking 3 kink bands propagation in cut sections

Fig. 17. Impactor projected contact surface measurements

Fig. 18. Determining principle of X45

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Fig. 19. Determining principle of stacking 2 stiffness

Carbon/epoxy T700/M21 UD properties		
ep	Ply thickness	0,25 mm
E_l	Tensile Young's modulus in fiber direction	135 GPa
E_c	Compressive Young's modulus in fiber direction	110 GPa
E_t	Transverse Young's modulus	8,5 GPa
G_{lt}	Shear modulus	4,2 GPa
ν_{lt}	Poisson's ratio	0,33
Failure		
X_T	Longitudinal tensile strength	2210 MPa
X_c	Longitudinal compressive strength	-1280 MPa
Y_T	Transverse tensile strength	75 MPa
Y_c	Transverse compressive strength	-250 MPa
S	In-plane shear strength	72 MPa

Tab. 1. T700/M21 mechanical properties

Carbon/epoxy M21/46280 fabric woven properties		
ep	Ply thickness	0,3 mm
E_l	Tensile Young's modulus in fiber direction	63,3 GPa
E_c	Compressive Young's modulus in fiber direction	- GPa
E_t	Transverse Young's modulus	63,3 GPa
G_{lt}	Shear modulus	5,1 GPa
ν_{lt}	Poisson's ratio	0,04
Failure		
X_T	Longitudinal tensile strength	690 MPa
X_c	Longitudinal compressive strength	-676 MPa
Y_T	Transverse tensile strength	690 MPa
Y_c	Transverse compressive strength	-616 MPa
S	In-plane shear strength	120 MPa

Tab. 2. M21/46280 mechanical properties

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